

Kirkwood-Buff Parameter for the Solubility of Gases in Water at High Pressure

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Pressure dependence gas solubilities of sparingly soluble gases like nitrogen, hydrogen, oxygen, carbon monoxide and nitrous oxide in water at 25° have been calculated with the help of thermodynamic functions using a statistical method of curve fitting. The approximate pressure ranges are : N₂ (25–120 atm), H₂ (25–120 atm), O₂ (10–90 atm), CO (25–105 atm) and NO (10–105 atm). The solubility data are analysed in terms of Kirkwood-Buff solution theory, and the role of hydrophobic interactions is discussed.

The solubility of gases in liquids has continued to be an area of active interest both from the practical and theoretical standpoint. For the first, interest ranges from various industrial processes to the composition of artificial atmospheres. For the second, the small solubility and the variety of gases available to use as probes have made the solubility of gases in liquids an excellent tool to investigate liquid and solution structures and properties.

The present communication gives a method of calculations of solubilities of gases in one special but important case, where the solubility of gases is small and vapour pressure of the solvent is not great. The solubilities in water of such important technical gases like nitrogen, hydrogen, oxygen, carbon monoxide and nitrous oxide fall in this classification.

The isothermal solubilities of small gases in liquids at sufficiently low pressure, are well-described by Henry's law,

$$\lim_{x_2 \rightarrow 0} [f_2/x_2] = K_H^0$$

where, f_2 is the fugacity of the solute above the solution and x_2 the mole-fraction of the solute in solution. Henry's law constant, K_H^0 is a characteristic of the solute-solvent system at a given temperature and provides direct informations on the unlike interactions of solute and solvent. Although interactions between like solvent molecules also enter, it has been assumed in many cases that their contribution to K_H^0 is insignificant.

Another motivation of this communication is to examine the role of hydrophobic effects on the gas solubilities. Hydrophobic effect is usually assumed to be a major factor influencing the immiscibility of water and solute substances, the thermodynamic properties of aqueous solutions, the conformation of proteins and nucleic acid in solutions, association equilibria in aqueous solutions, micelle formation by amphiphilic molecules and the stability of lipid bilayers and biological membranes. Here, the hydrophobic effect is described quantitatively in terms of the Kirkwood-Buff (K-B) integral G_{ij} , defined by¹

$$G_{ij} = \int_0^\infty [g_{ij}(r)-1] 4 \pi r^2 dr$$

The quantity G_{22} plays an important role in determining the concentration dependence of the chemical potential and is a measure of correlation among solute particles in solution. The physical significance of G_{22} may be understood in such a fashion that $\rho_2 G_{22}$ (ρ_2 is the number density of solute molecules) represents the average excess number of solute molecules surrounding a fixed solute molecule with respect to a uniform distribution². For example, if G_{22} is positive, the solute molecules are more correlated than if they are distributed randomly. This sort of solvent-induced clustering in aqueous solutions is commonly referred to as a hydrophobic interaction³.

Theory :

The system of interest contains two components, solute and solvent molecules, and consists of a liquid phase in equilibrium with a gas phase. We consider the special case where the solubility of solute is small and the vapour pressure of the solvent is low compared to the total pressure. When the vapour pressure of the solvent is small, the total pressure (P) can be identified with the partial pressure of the solute and the vapour pressure can be treated as consisting of solute molecules alone. The chemical potential, μ_2^g of the solute molecules in the vapour phase is then given by

$$\mu_2^g(T,P) = \mu_2^g(T) + RT \ln \left[\frac{f_2(T,P)}{P^0} \right] \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_2^g(T)$ is the standard chemical potential of the solute in the gas phase at temperature T and $f_2(T,P)$ is the fugacity. Here P^0 denotes the standard pressure of 1 atm. At constant temperature T , the chemical potential, μ_2^l of the solute molecules in liquid phase can be expressed in the differential form⁴,

$$(d\mu_2^l)_T = \left(\frac{\partial \mu_2^l}{\partial x_2} \right)_{P,T} dx_2 + \left(\frac{\partial \mu_2^l}{\partial P} \right)_{x_2,T} dP \quad (2)$$

The chemical potential of the solute molecules may be correlated with the K-B integrals as¹

$$\frac{1}{RT} \left(\frac{\partial \mu_2^l}{\partial x_2} \right)_{P,T} = \frac{1}{x_2} + \frac{\rho_1(2G_{12} - G_{11} - G_{22})}{1 + \rho_1 x_2(G_{11} + G_{22} - 2G_{12})} \quad (3)$$

For dilute solution, equation (3) can be expressed in the form^{1,5}.

$$\frac{1}{RT} \left(\frac{\partial \mu_2^l}{\partial x_2} \right)_{P,T} = \frac{1}{x_2} + \frac{1}{v_1^0} (-G_{22} + v_1^0 - 2v_2^0 + RT\beta_1) + O(x_2) \quad (4)$$

where, v_1^0 and v_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of solvent and solute in the solution respectively at infinite dilution, and β_1 is the isothermal compressibility of the pure solvent⁶. Integrating equation (4) and keeping the terms to first order in x_2 yields⁷

$$\mu_2^l(T, P, x_2) = D_1(T) + D_2(T) (P - P^0) + D_3(T) x_2 + RT \ln x_2 + O(x_2^2) \quad (5)$$

where, $D_1(T)$ is a constant depending only on temperature and $O(x_2^2)$ represents terms of second order in x_2 , and $D_2(T)$ and $D_3(T)$ are the thermodynamic quantities related to the derivatives of chemical potential.

If the solution is well below the critical temperature of the solvent and the partial molar volume is weakly dependent on pressure then, $D_2(T)$ can be described by the thermodynamic relation⁸,

$$D_2(T) = \left(\frac{\partial \mu_2^l}{\partial P} \right)_{m,T} = v_2 \quad (6)$$

$D_3(T)$ can be evaluated by standard thermodynamic reasoning

$$D_3(T) = \frac{RT}{v_1^0} (-G_{22} + v_1^0 - 2v_2^0 + RT\beta_1) \quad (7)$$

The equality of the chemical potential in the liquid and vapour phases gives

$$\ln \left[\frac{f_2(T, P)}{x_2 P^0} \right] = \frac{1}{RT} [D_1(T) + D_2(T) (P - P^0) + D_3(T) x_2 - \mu_2^g + O(x_2^2)] \quad (8)$$

At low pressure, this reduces to

$$\ln [P/x_2 P^0] = [1/RT] [D_1(T) - D_2(T) P^0 - \mu_2^g(T)] \quad (9)$$

At infinite dilution, as the left-hand-side of the equation (9) is nothing but the logarithm of Henry's law constant K_H^v , therefore equation (8) becomes

$$\ln \left[\frac{f_2(T, P)}{x_2 P^0} \right] = \ln K_H^v + \frac{1}{RT} [D_2(T) P + D_3(T) x_2 + O(x_2^2)] \quad (10)$$

This leads to the desired result,

$$\ln \left[\frac{f_2(T, P)}{x_2 P^0} \right] = \ln K_H^v + \frac{P v_2^0}{RT} + x_2 D_3(T)/RT + O'(x_2^2) \quad (11)$$

The only approximations made in deriving this result are that the vapour pressure of the solvent is negligible compared to the total pressure and the solution is dilute enough so that quadratic and higher order terms in equation (5) for the chemical potential of the solute are negligible and finally that the partial molar volumes are independent of pressure.

Thus the solubility data at high pressure can be analysed by plotting $[(\ln f_2/x_2 P^0) - P v_2^0/RT]$ against x_2 . The ordinate axis intercept of such a plot gives $\ln K_H^v$ and the low-pressure limiting slope, which is equal to $D_3(T)/RT$, enables G_{22} to be determined from equation (7).

Results and Discussion

There are only two types of gas solubilities studied : (i) those which have measured isothermally the solubility at various pressures, usually quite large ones and (ii) those which measured only a few points at the same temperature usually at a single pressure. The majority of the gas solubility data are reported for a single gas pressure at each temperature. Moreover, we have verified that reported variation of solubility with pressure (as in type-i) is strongly dependent on the author carrying the measurement and hence we believe that, with some notable exceptions, the reported dependence of solubility on pressure is mainly an artifact of the experimental set-up and the procedure employed. For this reason, in order to get concentration dependence partial pressure of the solute, we have taken the most reliable gas solubility data⁹ reported for a single gas pressure at a particular temperature and have extrapolated graphically this solubility value to $P = P^*$, the solvent saturated vapour pressure (P^*) for that temperature.

Fugacities can not be determined directly and are calculated from the partial pressure via

$$f_2 = P_2 e^{B_2 P_2 / RT}$$

where, B_2 is the second virial coefficient of the gas. The second virial coefficient for exp-6 potential requires numerical integration and may be expressed as

$$B_2(T) = b_0 B^*(T^*)$$

where, $b_0 = 2/3 (\pi N \sigma^3)$ and $T^* = KT/\epsilon$. Here σ is the distance between centres where the potential energy to zero and ϵ the maximum energy of attraction. The function $B^*(T^*)$ is tabulated in the Appendix of Ref. 10. The calculated values of fugacity are given in Table 1.

It has been shown that by using a semiempirical perturbation method, it is possible to determine the thermodynamics of dissolution of gases in water. With the help of perturbation theory applied by Neff and McQuarrie¹¹ and employing the values of hard sphere equivalent diameter of solutes¹⁰ and solvent¹² at the working temperature and the properties of pure solvent, it is possible to cal-

culate v_2^0 . The partial molar volume of solvent, v_1^0 at infinite dilution is assumed to be the molar volume of pure liquid. Both partial molar volumes are pressure-independent.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF PARTIAL PRESSURE OF THE GAS ON ITS MOLE FRACTION

Solute	x_2	P_2 atm	f_2 atm
H ₂	0.000 347 1	25.00	25.33
	0.000 519 5	38.02	38.79
	0.000 732 4	53.70	55.25
	0.000 889 5	66.07	68.42
	0.001 068 0	79.43	82.84
	0.001 338 6	100.00	105.43
	0.001 584 9	120.00	127.86
N ₂	0.000 296 1	25.12	25.23
	0.000 469 3	39.81	40.07
	0.000 652 1	54.95	55.45
	0.000 870 7	72.44	73.32
	0.001 033 4	87.10	88.37
	0.001 258 9	104.71	106.55
	0.001 435 9	120.23	122.66
O ₂	0.000 228 8	10.00	9.94
	0.000 454 1	19.95	19.79
	0.000 688 7	30.20	29.70
	0.000 936 3	41.69	40.74
	0.001 201 9	52.48	50.97
	0.001 533 6	69.18	66.57
	0.001 898 7	87.10	82.98
CO	0.000 425 2	25.00	24.67
	0.000 535 3	31.62	31.09
	0.000 716 9	42.66	41.70
	0.000 936 7	55.39	53.78
	0.001 218 2	72.44	69.69
	0.001 436 0	85.11	81.33
	0.001 692 7	111.00	95.70
NO	0.000 349 0	10.00	9.93
	0.000 880 4	25.12	24.70
	0.001 484 0	41.69	40.53
	0.002 062 0	57.54	55.35
	0.002 553 5	72.44	68.99
	0.003 059 9	87.10	82.13
	0.003 647 5	104.71	97.57

We have analysed the solubility calculation at high pressure for H₂, N₂, O₂, CO and NO in water at 25°. It has been found that, in general, the solubility data show a good internal consistency. The straight-lines are drawn from the least-square fit to data. The calculated slope is very sensitive to the choice of partial molar volumes and hence the accuracy of G_{22} determined from the present method depends on the accuracy of the values used for v_2^0 . The values of v_2^0 are taken from different references^{13,14} along with our own data. The intercepts of our graph are much less dependent on the choice of partial molar volume than the slope and agree well with the known experimental results. The values of G_{22} and in $\ln K_H^0$ calculated from these straight-lines are summarized in Table 2.

 TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF G_{22} ON PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME OF THE GAS

Solute	v_2^0 ml mol ⁻¹	G_{22} ml mol ⁻¹	$\ln K_H^0$ (calcd.)	$\ln K_H^0$ (expt.) ^a
H ₂	19.3 ^a	-305	11.178 3	11.170 0
	21.1 ^b	-206	11.178 5	
	18.9 ^c	-326	11.178 3	
N ₂	33.0 ^a	+1 998	11.351 1	11.365 1
	36.5 ^b	+2 205	11.351 1	
	32.5 ^c	+1 968	11.351 1	
O ₂	27.2 ^a	+870	10.676 1	10.689 7
	31.5 ^b	+1 007	10.676 3	
	25.8 ^c	+825	10.676 0	
CO	30.0 ^a	+1 718	10.982 8	10.971 6
	39.6 ^b	+2 122	10.983 0	
	28.5 ^c	+1 655	10.982 8	
NO	27.8 ^a	+889	10.253 3	10.26
	28.2 ^b	+859	10.253 3	

^aRef. 9. ^bPartial molar volume calculated by authors. ^cRef. 13. ^dRef. 14.

Assuming G_{22} as a function of total volume V and the partial molar volume of the solvent v_2^0 , the absolute error dG_{22} in the values of G_{22} obtained from this calculation may be evaluated from

$$dG_{22} = dv_1 [2x_1 v_1/V x_2^2 D] + dV [x_1 v_1^2/V^2 x_2^2 D] + dD [x_1 v_1^2/V x_2^2 D] + dV/x_2 + RT$$

where, $D = \frac{1}{x_2} + x_1 [d^2 Q/dx_2^2]$

$$= d \ln P_2/d x_2$$

$$Q = G^E / RT$$

and $dD = x_1 d(d^2 Q/d x_2^2)$

where, R is the gas constant, G^E the excess Gibbs energy per mole of the solute arises due to the intermolecular interactions in the gas and liquid phase. In order to perform differentiation of empirical functions, density $\rho = f(x_2)$ and $G^E = f(x_2)$, we have modified the sliding polynomial method¹⁵. The modification consisted in an elaboration of the algorithm of the choice of smoothing interval according to the residuas dispersion. The problem of determining the error of the derivative calculation can be solved by multiple simulation of the evaluated error of approximation of the experimental dependence with the subsequent determination of error limits for derivatives.

From the values of G_{22} obtained here, it is quite difficult to extract quantitative informations, though they provide a useful qualitative indications of the existence of the hydrophobic interactions. Examining the data on aqueous solutions of gases, it is necessary to point out a striking consequence that G_{22} is positive for most of the systems, indicating the existence of pairwise solute-solute attractions sufficiently large to overcome the solute size and hydration effect, i.e. these solutes in solutions tend to stay closer to each other as is expected. The only exception is hydrogen which exhibits what might facetiously be called 'hydrophobic repulsion' rather than 'hydrophobic attrac-

tion'. This suggests that although it does not want to go into water (i.e. the solubility is low) and hence it is in a sense hydrophobic, once it is in solution it prefers to be surrounded by water and in that sense, it is hydrophilic.

The ice-like cages which form around the solute in the clathrate phase could provide a mechanism for 'hydrophobic repulsion' between solutes. This tendency of the solutes to avoid one another in solution is reflected in the negative value of G_{22} for hydrogen. Same type of result was obtained by Watanabe and Andersen⁷ for Kr-water system. They found that $G_{22}(\text{Kr}) = -604 \text{ ml mol}^{-1}$, which indicates that Kr solutes tend to undergo 'hydrophobic repulsion' in solution.

We can split G_{22} into two parts : attractive (A_2^*) and repulsive (R_2^*) components. That is

$$\begin{aligned} G_{22} &= \int_0^\infty [g_{22}(r)-1]4\pi r^2 dr \\ &= \int_0^\sigma (-4\pi r^2)dr + \int_\sigma^\infty [g_{22}(r)-1] 4\pi r^2 dr \\ &= R_2^* + A_2^* \end{aligned}$$

where, σ is the distance of closest approach of two solute molecules. The first term results from the strongly repulsive region $r < \sigma$. According to Isihara¹⁶, $R_2^* = f (8v_2^0)$, where f is the factor which is a measure of ellipticity of the solute molecule. Except for the long-chain polymer molecules, the asymmetry factor f is not very different from the hardsphere value of unity. The second term can be identified qualitatively with an attractive region $r > \sigma$. A_2^* is a measure of the overall correlation, or the 'affinity' of one solute with respect to the other in the region $r > \sigma$. In the region of solute-solute attraction A_2^* is positive. Thus the sign and magnitude of G_{22} and hence the thermodynamic behaviour of given system, clearly depends on the relative contribution of attractive and repulsive regions. We next compare the quantity A_2^* obtained for different solutes. Table 3 shows that the effective interactions between solute molecules becomes more attractive as the size of the solute molecules increases.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SIZE OF THE GAS ON A_2^*

Solute	σ Å	A_2^* ml mol ⁻¹
H ₂	2.915	-151
N ₂	3.433	+1 088
O ₂	3.470	+1 111
CO	3.590	+1 958
NO	3.749	+2 262

To summarise briefly, we have found that the solubility data could be accurately fit by taking account only of the pressure effect on the solute chemical potential. Although solute-solute effect may play some role in the solvation process, the change in chemical potential at increased pressure is primarily due to the increased PV work to place the solute in the solvent. The contribution of solute-solute interactions expected at high concentration is uncertain, since the partial molar volumes of solutes are not known accurately enough.

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